

Triggers and Barriers of Rural Women Entrepreneurs : An Empirical Study

P. PARAMSHIVAIAH

Abstract : *Rural women entrepreneurship has been rising rapidly. More prominent businesses can be seen. Women entrepreneurs in rural area have taken up business activities on the basis of many driving forces. As Indian women in no way inferior to men in all walk of life and they are as good as men in entrepreneurial skills, it is imperative to exploit the potential of Indian women. Women's participation in trade, industry and commerce requires entrepreneurship. Studies have been done to understand the women entrepreneurs in general. Rural entrepreneurship is relatively under researched. The present study is an attempt to understand the triggers and barriers to women entrepreneurs in rural areas in particular. A sample of 280 respondents-in 10 villages of Hassan and Mysore District was collected through interview schedule. Factor analysis and ANOVA was applied to test the hypothesis. The results show that there is no difference in the opinion of respondents about triggers where as there is no common opinion, i.e. no common problems to all the types of businesses. Every type of enterprise has its own problems. We suggest for government financial assistance to rural women and educational support. We also recommend enhancing the women outlook by improving a positive attitude.*

Keywords : Women Entrepreneurs, Rural, Triggers, Barriers, Attitude.

INTRODUCTION

About 50 percent of total population constitutes women, but women workers constitute only 16 percent, 80 percent remain engaged in unorganized sectors. The entrepreneurial world is still a male dominated one. According to the United Nations Human Development Report (2002) in India women work 457 minutes per day and men 391. The type of activities men and women do explains why women work more time than men but their estimated income is lower. Women

spend 65% of their time in non-market activities, and men spend 92% of their time in market activities. However, the number of women entrepreneurs is rising rapidly and many are creating Substantial businesses Women in advanced nations are recognized and are more prominent in the business field. But the Indian women entrepreneurs are facing some major constraints. Women are expected to perform the domestic and reproductive tasks like cooking, cleaning, collection of fuel wood and water, care for the animals, child bearing and rearing. This type of mentality imposes restrictions on their mobility and on their contacts with the outside world, restrains their access to jobs and their social and political participation in the society. They are dependent on men, economically, socially and politically, and have limited direct independent access to resources.

‘Women Entrepreneur’ is a person who accepts challenging role to meet her personal needs and become economically self-sufficient. Entrepreneurship among rural women is a recent phenomenon.

Rural Women entrepreneurs may be defined as a woman or group of women, who initiate, organize and run a business enterprise in villages or sub-urban areas. According to Schumpeter women who innovate, imitate or adopt a business activity are called “women entrepreneurs”.

Need and Importance of the Study

Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru, realizing the pathetic situation of women, stated, “in order to awaken people, it is the woman who has to be awakened. Once she is on the move, the household moves, the village moves, the country moves, and thus, we build the India of tomorrow. As Indian women in no way inferior to men in all walk of life and they are as good as men in entrepreneurial skills, it is imperative to exploit the potential of Indian women. Women’s participation in trade, industry and commerce requires entrepreneurship. It is observed that entrepreneurial traits are still poor mainly because of the problems associated with their traditional role in the family. In rural areas, women are helping men in agriculture and agri-business industries. With little training and support they can prove better results in the business activities. Setting up of small business units generates income to the family and it contributes to the national economy through commercial activities and employment generation. Women in rural area engaged in businesses like bakery, dairy, poultry, milk-parlor, beauty parlor, general stores and small spare parts, flower vending etc. Many of the traditional occupations open to women are mainly based on caste, creed and the nature of self-employment is based on the standard of living. At present, women are

generating employment for themselves in unorganized sectors and other category of women provides employment for others.

Contribution of the Study

Like any other investigations that lead to policy initiatives, the present study explores the major motivating factors and barriers to rural women to become an entrepreneur in Indian context. Understanding the typical problems of the rural women folk as an entrepreneur paves the way for nurturing the occupation through needful support and required policy from the government. Removing the barriers to the success of rural women entrepreneurs contribute to a greater extent to align themselves in the right direction. Moreover, rural entrepreneurship is relatively less researched. This study contributes to the literature on this area in the Indian context.

Statement of the Problem

Many research studies prove that women empowerment and financial self sufficiency is achieved through entrepreneurial activities. Many NGOs have been training women in this direction. Plenty of women have successful in the field of business and achieved fame globally. Generally, women in the urban areas have been engaging in trade and business activities, at least, in small scale. As the concept of urbanization of rural is the order of the day, government focusing on development infrastructure at the gross route level, and also, encouraging rural women to set up business or self-employment activities. Women in the rural areas are gradually coming forward to start up enterprises through which enhancing their level of socio-economic status. Because of its success in many cases, rural entrepreneurship has been gaining popularity. Although women entrepreneurs are being inspired by the success stories, there are instances of obstacles to it. Hence, studying the triggers and barriers to rural women entrepreneurship is a concern.

Review of Literature

There are few studies investigated the major issues of women entrepreneurs in rural areas. They stressed that the socio-economic problems of the rural women entrepreneurs to be addressed soon.

Cole (1959), in their study on rural women entrepreneurs, observed that another important business motivation for women is the need to provide security to the family.

A study done by **Azad (1982)**, reveals that the main motivating factors for women entrepreneurs are economic compulsion, the presence of knowledge and skills, need for achievement, inspiration gathered from the success of others and frustration in the present occupation.

The research by **Asghari (1983)**, concludes that women take up entrepreneurship to fulfill economic needs like power and achievement and to gain a novel experience.

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Nelson (1991), in his study, *Small Business Opportunities for Women in Jamaica*, revealed that women were concentrated in businesses which required the least capital outlay or an extension of household activities. The study also revealed that women entrepreneurs were dependent on their business to maintain their homes and support their families

O D Heggade (1998) has discussed the development of rural women entrepreneurship, trends, and patterns of growth by various types of economic activities and the problems faced by them. The government schemes such as DWCRA/TRYSEM and other income generating activities in the group and by individual entrepreneurs have enlightened the process involved in the promotion of self- help groups, networking of the bankers/NGOs/village panchayats/departments/societies in organizing and promoting self-employment ventures by these women. The study has revealed that the marginalized groups like SC/STs, religious minorities like Muslims/Christians are very negligible whereas the rural women belonging to Hindu forward groups are substantial. Activities selected by these women were purely village based, lacked tapping the avenues of wider markets due to gender bias of the promoters, their restrictions in mobility, constraints of market expansion ideas by taking additional working capital. The author has failed to comment on the personality growth of these women, and mode of inculcating risk taking, decision making, and capacity building aspects.

Punitha et al. (1999), examined the problems and constraints faced by self-employed women in the Pondicherry region. A sample of 120 women was personally interviewed during the period from June to July 1999 of which 42 belonged to rural and 78 to urban areas. The major problems faced by the rural

self-employed women were competition from better quality products, and marketing problems. The problems for the urban entrepreneurs were, apart from the competition from better quality products, the difficulty in getting loans. The least problems faced by both rural and urban self-employed women were ignorance about schemes, distance from markets, and ignorance about agencies and institutions

Lall & Sahai, (2008), conduct a comparative assessment of multi-dimensional issues & challenges of women entrepreneurship, & family business. The study identified Psychographic variables like, degree of commitment, entrepreneurial challenges & future plan for expansion, based on demographic variables. Through stratified random sampling & convenience sampling the data have been collected from women entrepreneurs working in urban area of Lucknow. The study identified business owner's characteristics as self-perception, self-esteem, Entrepreneurial intensity & operational problem for future plans for growth & expansion. The study suggested that though, there has been considerable growth in number of women opting to work in family owned.

Sathiabama. K (2010), in her article titled 'Rural Women Empowerment and Entrepreneurship Development' emphasized empowerment of rural women through entrepreneurship and the advantages entrepreneurship among the rural women, in some countries, women may experience obstacles with respect to holding property and entering contracts. They suggest that increased participation of women in the labour force is a prerequisite for improving the position of women in society and self-employed women. They also advise that the need is knowledge regarding accessibility to loans, various funding agencies procedure regarding certification, awareness on government welfare programmes, motivation, technical skill and support from family, government and other organization. More over Formation and strengthening of rural women Entrepreneurs' network must be encouraged.

Kishor N. Choudhary & Dr. Arvind P.Royalwar (2011) studied Opportunities and Challenges for Rural women Entrepreneurship in India and highlight some issues with reference to the strategic challenges and opportunities from a gender focus to analyze the prospects of rural small and medium entrepreneurship for women.

S. Vargheese Antony Jesurajan and S. Varghees Prabhu (2012) conduct an empirical investigation entitled on the Expectation of women entrepreneurs in Tirunelveli district of Tamilnadu. This study aims to study the expectations of

women entrepreneurs in Tirunelveli district. The number of samples collected for this study is 300 women entrepreneurs and the type of sampling used is proportionate stratified random sampling. Factors analysis has been employed for the purpose of analyzing the data. The finding depicts many factors like finance, training, support and schemes are the major expectations among the women entrepreneurs in Tirunelveli district. This study will be relevant and significant to the present Indian scenario.

Sreenivasa Rao Behara & K Niranjana (2012), in their study of rural women entrepreneurship in India, intends to find out various problems, motivating and de-motivating factors of women entrepreneurship. This study is based on secondary data only. They found that Desire to be independent; achievement orientation, etc. are some of the common motivating factors of women entrepreneurs across geographical boundaries. Women entrepreneurs in India have to face many problems at start up as well as operating stage. The main reason of non-availability of finance to women is their inability to provide collaterals as they do not have any property on their name. Women have got restricted mobility, and freedom, and have to perform dual roles at family and at business as well, which hinders the entrepreneurial growth. Similarly some gender related stereotypes also create obstacles for women entrepreneurs. They trace that the social systems and attitudes the root cause of these problems.

Anitha D.Pharm, & Dr. R. Sritharan (2013), in their study, entitled 'Problems being faced by women entrepreneurs in rural areas', focused on the women entrepreneurs in selected districts in ERODE district, Tamilnadu. They tried highlighting their motivational forces and relationship between socio-economic background of women entrepreneurs, motivational factors and their existing entrepreneurial traits. In their study, through various tools, suggest that marketing product is the main problem for women entrepreneurs. They also found that improper location and inadequate infrastructure facilities are the hurdles in the way of development of women entrepreneurship

Research Gap

Literature study reveals many issues of rural women entrepreneurs. No research work has focused on the multi-dimensional issues of the research topic. Problems of rural women entrepreneurship are multi-faceted. Triggers and barriers of rural entrepreneurship of different types of businesses on socio-economic angle is the research gap that we found out. Hence, we proceed to understand the triggers and barriers of rural women entrepreneurs.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

OBJECTIVES

The purpose of the paper is to Study of triggers and barriers of rural women entrepreneurs. Therefore, we set the following objectives for the study

- To understand the socio-economic status of respondents in the study area
- To study the triggers for rural entrepreneurship among the respondents
- To understand the problems of rural women entrepreneurs
- To suggest measures to overcome barriers and motivate rural women entrepreneurs

HYPOTHESES

For the study we set the following hypothesis :

- H_{01} : there is no significant difference in the mean perception of respondents as regard triggers
- H_{11} : there is significant difference in the mean perception of respondents as regards triggers
- H_{02} : there is no significant difference in the mean perception of respondents as regards barriers
- H_{12} : there is a significant difference in the mean perception of respondents as regards barriers

DATA COLLECTION

The present study is empirical and descriptive in nature based on both primary and secondary data. Secondary data has been collected from journals, working papers, newspapers, thesis, books, and reports published on the relevant topic. Simple random sampling and systematic sampling method was followed for this study.

Primary data consists of responses collected from women entrepreneurs in rural areas, running different types of businesses. In a structured interview, the schedule was prepared, and the same questions were posed to all the respondents in the same order. Each question was asked in the same way in each interview,

for the purpose of measurement of reliability. In the present study, Likert's summated scale was used at five points.

Data Validation

Data was validated by applying Cronbach's alpha method.

SAMPLING :

The Sampling frame is the women entrepreneurs in rural areas. 10 villages and sub-urban towns, of population not more than 10000, were considered for data collection. In each area women entrepreneurs were met. Respondents not participated were ignored from the list. Total sample of 280 respondents were finally considered for analysis.

Locale of the Study :

Villages selected from Hassan and Mysore District where we found many women business enterprises of different types.

Period of the Study

The study has been undertaken from October 2022 to July 2023.

Scope of the Study :

The study includes women entrepreneurs who are engaged in small businesses of different types in rural areas. The study explores the triggers and barriers of rural women entrepreneurs in general. Includes those run their businesses in rural areas itself and those who move to urban areas regularly for business. Triggers we mean the driving force behind choosing entrepreneurship and barriers address the typical problems of women entrepreneurs in general and rural women in particular.

TOOLS FOR ANALYSIS

Data so obtained was analyzed by using SPSS version 16.0. Percentage, mean, , Factor analysis and ANOVA were applied for data analysis, after testing the reliability of the data.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The study of socio-economic background of respondents was relevant before we go for various testing. Respondents were classified on the basis of age,

education, family background, and annual income. Cross tabulation of nature of business and 10 villages shows the various types of business in each village. Of the total respondents, 32 members family background is farm labour, a major chunk of 132 members from agriculture background, 79 members have business background basically from chettiers, Muslims, Marwaris community, a small percent are of other community members, whereas 37 members running their business on the basis of traditional caste based occupation, particularly broomstick vendors, flower vendors and beauty-parlors

TABLE-1 : SOCIO-ECONOMIC PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS											
Family background											
		Farm labours		Agriculture		Trade/Business		Caste- occupation		Sub Total	
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
AGE	20-35	11	34.4	44	33.3	24	30.4	10	27.0	89	31.8
	35-50	17	53.1	67	50.8	46	58.2	23	62.2	153	54.6
	>50	4	12.5	21	15.9	9	11.4	4	10.8	38	13.6
	Subtotal	32	100.0	132	100.0	79	100.0	37	100.0	280	100.0
Education	UP TO 7th	9	28.1	18	13.6	6	7.6	9	24.3	42	15.0
	8th - 10th	15	46.9	54	40.9	40	50.6	18	48.6	127	45.4
	10th & above	8	25.0	60	45.5	33	41.8	10	27.0	111	39.6
	Subtotal	32	100.0	132	100.	79	100.0	37	100.0	280	100.0
MARITAL STATUS	Married	19	59.4	103	78.0	74	93.7	27	73.0	223	79.6
	single	9	28.1	26	19.7	5	6.3	10	27.0	50	17.9
	Widow	4	12.5	3	2.3	0	.0	0	.0	7	2.5
	Subtotal	32	100.0	132	100.0	79	100.0	37	100.0	280	100.0
Annual Income	Below 20000	7	21.9	40	30.3	18	22.8	13	35.1	78	27.9
	20000-40000	10	31.2	58	43.9	44	55.7	21	56.8	133	47.5
	Above 40000	15	46.9	34	25.8	17	21.5	3	8.1	69	24.6
	Subtotal	32	100.0	132	100.0	79	100.0	37	100.0	280	100.0

Source: field study

15 percent of respondents are educated below 7th standard, 45.4 percent are up to 10th standard, and 39 percent are above 10th standard. 79 percent of women

are married, 17.9 percent are unmarried and 2.5 percent are widows. In the income category, 47.5 percent members are earning income up to Rs.40000 And 27 percent of the respondents are earning income only up to 20000 annually, where as 24.6 percent of the respondents earn over Rs.40000 annually. It is interesting to note, that 103 respondents who are married and running a business are from agriculture background and 19 members’ parents are farm labours. 74 entrepreneurs have business background.

Table-2 below indicates the number of respondents classified according to the nature of business in their respective villages. It is evident from the analysis that more than 30 women (10 percent) are engaged in selling flower, bangles, vegetable and a major chunk of the respondents are running general store or provision store consisting of provisions and goods for daily needs of the people in the locality. 20-30 members are milk sellers, fruit sellers, tailoring service, and running small canteen or bakery. 10- 20 members are engaged in spare parts trading, beauty-parlor and selling ropes and broomsticks produced by them and only 9 members are running small beauty-parlours.

Table-2 : The Number of Respondents Classified According to the Nature

Nature of business	v1	v2	v3	v4	v5	v6	v7	v8	v9	v10	Total
1. General store	4	3	4	4	5	3	3	4	3	3	36
2. Vegetable seller	1	5	3	4	2	6	2	4	4	1	32
3. Fruit seller	1	2	2	4	2	0	3	3	0	3	20
4. Bangle seller	4	2	3	1	3	3	3	6	4	3	32
5. Tailoring	3	4	2	1	2	2	2	0	4	4	24
6. Rope and broomstick vendor	5	0	1	2	0	1	3	1	1	3	17
7. Milk seller	3	6	2	2	2	3	3	2	3	1	27
8. Flower vendor	3	2	4	3	2	3	3	2	4	5	31
9. Small canteen/bakery/fruit juice centre	2	1	3	5	4	2	1	3	3	3	27
10. Coconut vendor	1	1	0	1	1	2	3	0	0	0	9
11. Beauty parlor	0	1	3	0	4	3	0	2	1	1	15
12. Spare parts store	1	1	1	1	1	0	2	1	1	1	10
Total	28	280									

SOURCE: FIELD WORK

FACTOR ANALYSIS :

To understand the driving force behind the rural women entrepreneurs, 16 statements were asked and recorded as per their priority. Factor analysis was applied to reduce the statements into factors. Initially, KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sampling adequacy (Table-3) was tested.

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.656
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1736.065
	df	120
	Sig.	.000

Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant, supporting the factorability of the correlation matrix and the associated significance level was extremely small (**0.000**). A high value which is above 0.5 to 1.0 generally indicates that a factor analysis may be useful with the data. As here KMO value is 0.656 on triggers perceived is more than 0.50, we found that the results of factor analysis are useful with the present data.

For factor extraction, principal component method was used, under the restriction that the Eigen value of each generated factor was more than one. A factor analysis was conducted to develop constructs that will help to evaluate factors that are identified as motivational force. Five factors were generated, which explained 62.15 percent of the variance with the loss of only 37.85 percent of information. The extracted factors were then rotated using variance maximizing method (Varimax). These rotated factors with their variable constituents and factor loadings are given in **Table 4**. Of the Five factors identified Opportunities is the first factor emerged as an important component with the highest factor scoring and the total variance of 26.092 percent, the second factor is Entrepreneurial Attitude with the total variance of 12.918 percent, then follow Career objective, Empowerment goal and Individual Talent. It is evident from the analysis, that rural women, if an opportunity available, can start and run businesses competitively and achieve her socio-economic self-sufficiency.

TABLE 4: FACTOR ANALYSIS

	Component					Eigen values	Cronbach's Alpha
	1	2	3	4	5		
Triggers from opportunities							
13. Existing local resources for running a business	.903						0.627
8. To utilize my skill and knowledge	.857					4.175	0.639
6. Unsuitable working opportunity	.852					(26.092)	0.635
16. Caste based occupation	.809						0.632
7. Previous Job dissatisfaction	.766						0.655
Entrepreneurial attitude							
15. Family business background		.794					0.679
4. Earning money for livelihood		.677				2.067	0.659
5. An Attractive sources of Income		.585				(12.918)	0.645
2. To prove my potential		.550					0.671
Career objective						1.381	
9. Education background			.887				0.700
3. To achieve socio-economic Status			.710			(8.632)	0.666
Empowerment goal						1.239	
14. Opportunity to run a new venture in the village				.866			0.672
1. I Desire to be Independent				.583		(7.741)	0.659
Individual talent						1.083	
12. Competencies and experience					.790		0.711
10. Family Support					.782	(6.768)	0.709

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations. b. Figures in the parenthesis are total variance

TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS 1

Our null hypothesis (H_{01}) is that there is no significant difference among the respondents as regards the motivational factors. We applied ONE-WAY ANOVA for the test.

TABLE 5: ANOVA

PERCEPTION	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between People	361.050	279	1.294		
Within People				1.991	.013
Between Items	12.296	15	.820		
Residual	1723.079	4185	.412		
Total	1735.375	4200	.413		
Total	2096.425	4479	.468		

Grand Mean = 1.17

The table (5) shows that F statistics equals 1.991 with a corresponding P-value 0.013. Since P-value is greater than 0.05 there is no enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis and infer that there is no significant differences in the mean perception of respondents. F statistics is less than the table value at 10 percent level of significance.

The third objective of the study is to understand the barriers or problems being faced by rural women entrepreneurs. For this purpose, again we applied Factor analysis. Reliability test was conducted for all 17 factors. The overall value of Cronbach's Alpha is 0.833 as shown below. The value more than 0.60 which is considered to be reliable and it shows the homogeneity of items.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.833	17

Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant, supporting the factorability of the correlation matrix and the associated significance level was extremely small (0.000). As here KMO value is 0.0.852 on triggers perceived is more than 0.50, we found that the results of factor analysis are useful with the present data.

TABLE 6: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.852
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	4744.037
	df	136
	Sig.	.000

TABLE 7: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigen values		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	5.954	35.024	35.024
2	4.585	26.970	61.994
3	2.093	12.312	74.306
4	.977	5.749	80.055

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Three factors were generated, which explained 80.05 percent of the variance with the loss of only 19.05 percent of information. The extracted factors were then rotated using variance maximizing method (Varimax). These rotated factors with their variable constituents and factor loadings are given in **Table 8**. Of the Three factors identified Economic Barriers is the first factor emerged as an important component with the highest factor scoring and the total variance of 35.024 percent, the second factor is psychological Barriers with the total variance of 26.970 percent, the third factor is social problems with total variance of 12.312 percent. It is evident from the analysis, that rural women, if an opportunity available, can start and run businesses competitively and achieve her socio-economic self-sufficiency. It is evident from the table that of the responses expressed, lack of family support is the main Sociological barrier. Difficulty in Relationship with suppliers, customers and others is the major psychological barrier. It is very pertinent from the analysis that most of the rural women are facing Economic problems and lack of technical and managerial skill and knowledge.

TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS 2

Our second null hypothesis (H_{02}) states that there is no significant difference in the mean perception of respondents as far as barriers are concerned. ONE-WAY ANOVA (Table 9) was calculated for this test. F statistics shown in the table equals 4.973 with a corresponding P-value 0.00 which is less than 0.05. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis and can be inferred that there is a significant difference between the mean perceptions of respondents as far as problems are concerned.

TABLE 8: FACTOR ANALYSIS

BARRIERS	Component		
	1	2	3
Economic Barriers			
2. Lack of Technical/management knowledge	.972		
8. Lack of proper training on innovative business practices	.963		
3. Financial problem	.930		
7. Problem of availability of raw materials	.923		
6. Problem of marketing my product/service	.885		
11. Exploitation by middle men	.869		
12. High competition from competitor and male counterparts	.824		
Psychological Barriers			
16. Difficulties in Relationship with suppliers, customers and others		.902	
13 Lack of self confidence		.892	
14. Lack of entrepreneurial aptitude		.884	
20. Unable to deal with legal formalities		.830	
15. Low risk-bearing capacity		.815	
21. Dual responsibility of family and business		.683	
19. Old and traditional outlook of society towards women as an entrepreneur		.562	
Social Barriers			
22. Lack of support from family members			.880
23. Negative attitude of male counterparts and public towards women entrepreneurs			.732
24. Lack of Public acceptance			.633

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 4 iterations.

TABLE 9: ANOVA

PERCEPTION	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between People	1434.689	279	5.142		
Within People					
Between Items	68.406	16	4.275	4.973	.000
Residual	3837.829	4464	.860		
Total	3906.235	4480	.872		
Total	5340.924	4759	1.122		

Grand Mean = 1.53

Women in rural area in particular are hardworking people. They are bold and prefer to be self-reliant. Most of them are frustrated with the daily wages that is insufficient to lead life and get their children educated, have comfortable house, and to have handsome income. Some of them are running business as a continuation to their parents or as a supportive entrepreneur. Rural women try to find new avenue in which they can continue their occupation perpetually. From the analysis it is found that women are diverging from agricultural activities and find new opportunities to earn income. They take up challenging venture too. Factor analysis revealed that most of them have intention to utilize their talent and educational background, perhaps they have Business education or some of them are engineering graduates traditionally struck in the villages on account of the typical social constraints where in the family members do not allow them to work outside as per their qualification. In this background rural entrepreneurship could be an alternative forum to exhibit and encash their skills. And also increasing needs of rural population and varied goods and services they desire to buy and consume in villages not less than urban population. Bakery, canteen, small hotels, beauty parlors, flower decoration for different occasions, milk, butter, ghee, cheese, tender coconut, fancy stores are found generally in rural areas now-a-days.

Rural entrepreneurship leads to increased business activities and income, and economic empowerment of women. Despite the opportunity, the driving spirit, self-motivation rural women entrepreneurs lack family support. This can be attributed to nuclear family trend and migration of educated youth towards cities. It is also found that the dual role of women is another important problem since she has to manage traditional functions of family and business. Of the problems they have been facing, economic problems such as low managerial talent, lack of finance, lack of supply of goods or material at reasonable price, lack of training and severe competition from their male counterpart.

SUGGESTIONS

To be successful, women entrepreneurs should have self-confidence, managerial skills, and technical and legal guidance, economic support in time. Therefore, in addition to the existing schemes of the government, NGOs and government together design a plan of action to make rural women more active, more positive in their attitude, instill confidence through financial and legal support. MAHILA BANK, MAHILA MARKET, Preference to buy products of women home industry, reservation to women in SEZ and Industrial sites, loans at cheaper rate of interest etc could stabilize the inspiration of rural women entrepreneurs.

To overcome sociological barriers, government has to educate through bulletins, news and advertisements to persuade them to not to bother about silly outlook of society. The attitude of male and the society towards women has been gradually becoming healthy. Rural women shall develop positive attitude and take out their inferiority from their mind.

LIMITATIONS AND SCOPE FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

The present study has a limited scope of only few villages of two districts and the sample size may not replicate and results may not be generalized. As the problems differ from business to business and locality and personal traits, the perception expressed are not applicable to different business and different people. The major occupation in rural area is agriculture. Naturally we cannot expect the qualities of typical business person. As the size of business is generally small, small is beautiful only when it is managed by trained entrepreneur. Therefore, the study did not focus the problems on the basis of nature of business. This is due to time and resource constraint. Thus, further study can be extended to examination of motivations and barriers with respect to a specific type of business either as a case study or in general.

CONCLUSION

After review of available literature, we undertook a study of trigger and problems of rural women entrepreneurs by collecting responses through interview schedule. Both motivational factors and problems of rural women entrepreneurship were analyzed through factor analysis and data was reduced to construct important factor. The hypothesis test proves that there is no difference in the perception about triggers. However, hypothesis test proved that there is no common opinion about the problems. Therefore, it is understood that problems of one entrepreneur may not be the same for other. It depends on the nature of business and other variables. However, it is suggested that the government financial and educational support is necessary and advised to mould and develop an entrepreneurial attitude positively.

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